

Appendix A: Maps

Here, we present the maps of molecules with low S/N and those which show very compact brightness distributions.

Fig. A.1. ALMA maps per velocity channel of $^{13}\text{CO } J=2-1$ emission in R Aqr. The LSR velocities are indicated in the upper-left corners. The brightness units are Jy beam^{-1} . The contours are logarithmic, with a step of a factor of two and a first level of $\pm 3 \text{ mJy beam}^{-1}$. The dashed contours represent negative values. The HPBW is shown in the inset in the last panel.

Fig. A.2. Same as Fig. A.1 but for $^{13}\text{CO } J=3-2$ using a first level of $\pm 4 \text{ mJy beam}^{-1}$.

Fig. A.3. Same as Fig. A.1 but for $\text{H}_2\text{O } v_2=2 J_{K_a,K_c}=3_{2,1}-4_{1,4}$ using a first level of $\pm 4 \text{ mJy beam}^{-1}$.

Fig. A.4. Same as Fig. A.1 but for $^{30}\text{SiO } \nu=3 J=8-7$ using a first level of $\pm 4 \text{ mJy beam}^{-1}$.

Fig. A.5. Same as Fig. A.1 but for $^{12}\text{CO } \nu=1 J=3-2$ using a first level of $\pm 4 \text{ mJy beam}^{-1}$.

Fig. A.6. Same as Fig. A.1 but for $\text{SO } ^3\Sigma \nu=1 N_J=9_8-8_7$ using a first level of $\pm 4 \text{ mJy beam}^{-1}$.

Fig. A.7. Same as Fig. A.1 but for SO $v=0$ $J=8-7$ using a first level of ± 4 mJy beam $^{-1}$.

Fig. A.8. Same as Fig. A.1 but for TiO $v=1$ $J_{K_a,K_c}=20_{2,121}-19_{2,120}$ using a first level of ± 25 mJy beam $^{-1}$.

Fig. A.9. Same as Fig. A.1 but for ^{49}TiO $J=20-19$ using a first level of ± 15 mJy beam $^{-1}$.

Fig. A.10. Same as Fig. A.1 but for $^{28}\text{SiO } v=4 J=16-15$ using a first level of $\pm 20 \text{ mJy beam}^{-1}$.

Fig. A.11. Same as Fig. A.1 but for U675616 using a first level of $\pm 15 \text{ mJy beam}^{-1}$.

Fig. A.12. Same as Fig. A.1 but for A10 $N=18-17$ using a first level of $\pm 20 \text{ mJy beam}^{-1}$.

Fig. A.13. Same as Fig. A.1 but for U689075 using a first level of ± 20 mJy beam $^{-1}$.

Fig. A.14. Same as Fig. A.1 but for TiO $_2$ $J_{K_a,K_c}=17_{10,8}-16_{9,7}$ using a first level of ± 25 mJy beam $^{-1}$. Emission of the AIF $J_F=21_{41/2}-20_{43/2}$ line is shown from -40.6 to -29.4 km s $^{-1}$ LSR.

Fig. A.15. Same as Fig. A.1 but for AIF $J_F=21_{41/2}-20_{43/2}$ using a first level of ± 22 mJy beam $^{-1}$. Emission of the TiO $_2$ $J_{K_a,K_c}=17_{10,8}-16_{9,7}$ line is shown from -13.4 to -5.4 km s $^{-1}$ LSR.

Fig. A.16. Same as Fig. A.1 but for $\text{H}_2\text{O } v_3=1 J_{K_a,K_c}=5_{7,2}-6_{6,1}$ using a first level of $\pm 22 \text{ mJy beam}^{-1}$. Absorption and emission of the $\text{SiO } v=9 J=17-16$ and $^{12}\text{CO } v=0 J=6-5$ lines are shown from -45.4 to -40.6 km s^{-1} and from -11.8 to -5.4 km s^{-1} LSR, respectively.

Fig. A.17. Same as Fig. A.1 but for $\text{SiO } v=9 J=17-16$ using a first level of $\pm 25 \text{ mJy beam}^{-1}$. Emission of the $\text{H}_2\text{O } v_3=1 J_{K_a,K_c}=5_{7,2}-6_{6,1}$ line is shown from -10.2 to -5.4 km s^{-1} LSR.

Fig. A.18. Same as Fig. A.1 but for $^{13}\text{CS } J=15-14$ using a first level of $\pm 25 \text{ mJy beam}^{-1}$.